

**METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS AND SCIENTIFIC-
THEORETICAL IMPORTANCE OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE
ABILITIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS.**

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Improving the quality of learning by primary school students is one of the most important tasks of the school. Many teachers achieve it by improving the forms and methods of teaching, and not at the expense of additional workload for students. In solving this problem, teachers and methodologists attach great importance to developing the interest of young students in learning by forming creative abilities in the work process. Due to the psychological characteristics of children of primary school age, their creative abilities are actively developing in the first years of study. In particular, to solve developmental educational goals, primary school teacher A.V. Nikitina organizes regular, appropriate development and activation of creative activity in a system that meets the following requirements: [18; p. 256]

cognitive tasks should be built on an interdisciplinary basis and should contribute to the development of mental characteristics of a person (memory, attention, thinking, imagination);

tasks should be selected taking into account the reasonable sequence of their presentation;

from reproductive ones aimed at updating existing knowledge, partly from research-oriented ones, aimed at mastering generalized methods of knowledge activity, and then allowing those who are actually creative to look at the studied phenomena from different angles;

the system of cognitive and creative tasks should lead to the formation of fluency of thinking, flexibility of the mind, curiosity, the ability to propose and develop hypotheses.

Such tasks are given to the whole class. Only success will be assessed when they are completed. Such tasks are educational and developmental rather than evaluative. Classes are conducted at a much faster pace from the front. According to A.V. Nikitina, such work creates a competitive spirit, focuses attention, develops the ability to quickly switch from one type to another.

A.L. Yujaninova [21; p. 122] developed and tested a development program aimed at increasing the creative activity of young students. The main condition of

creative works, according to him, is the organization of interactions between children and adults in accordance with the principles of humanistic psychology:

1) Admiring every student's idea is like admiring a child's first steps:

- a) positive reinforcement of all student's ideas and answers;
- b) using a mistake as an opportunity for a new, unexpected look at something familiar;
- c) maximal adaptation to all statements and actions of children.

2) to create an environment of mutual trust, selflessness, acceptance of others, and psychological safety.

3) ensuring independence in decision-making and choice, with the ability to independently manage one's own development.

Malov S.E. [12; p. 133] developed a program for developing creative abilities of schoolchildren by organizing group cooperation. Elementary school teacher Shubnikova E.G. [20; p. 123] uses the possibilities of lessons to develop imagination and creative thinking on school educational materials and to adapt games and exercises for their use in the process of teaching the Russian language, to increase the creative activity of young students:

- different types of essays, presentations, creative dictations;
 - construction (building sentences, drawing verbal pictures, making plans according to schemes, words and sentences);
 - making tables, diagrams; "discovering" word formation methods;
 - analyze literary works to prove any hypothesis; distribution of offers;
 - agreeing with endings for stories; draw pictures using templates;
 - publication of newspapers and magazines using the results of children's creativity (notes, interviews, reviews, essays, poems, fairy tales, pictures, rebuses, puzzles, crosswords, etc.);
 - creating films for literary works;
 - staging of pictures, dramatization, "animation";
 - selection of characteristics (what can be a smile, walk, etc.);
 - create visual, sound, tasteful images of letters;
 - choosing synonyms, antonyms; study of phraseological turns;
- as a result of the analysis of the practical experience of increasing the creative activity of junior schoolchildren, first of all, the importance of this problem for teachers, the interest of psychologists and methodologists in it;
- secondly, the programs, courses, and a number of tasks presented in the scientific-methodical literature and periodicals on this issue have been developed and tested;

and thirdly, teachers' psychological on this issue low pedagogical competence; fourthly, the techniques and means of work in this direction, lack of systematic, purposeful work on increasing the creative activity of elementary school students due to lack of knowledge of its forms and, as a result, low levels of creative activity development of primary school students.

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